

Causes of Rheumatism and Methods of Treatment in Modern Medicine

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Abstract: This of the article purpose Rheumatism the disease modern in medicine determination and treatment methods with get to know Modern of medicine this disease diagnosis and in prevention place about to understanding have to be , rheumatism the disease in treatment modern of medicine possibilities and importance analysis from doing consists of.

Keywords: Rheumatism, hemolytic Streptococcus, Rheumatologist, Chorea, Rheumatic attack, neutrophil leukocytosis, FKG, Rheumatic fever, subfebrile the body temperature.

Introduction: Rheumatism — joints, muscles and binder of tissues inflamed damage with passing support - action system of diseases common name Basically tropical and Hot climatic countries wide spread out this disease "Rheumatic fever", "Sokolsky - Buyo disease" names also known as Russian in 1838 doctor AISokolsky and French scientist Buy it joint of rheumatism clinic with treatment the first times describing the disease heart damage directly connection that there is determined. This disease with mostly between 6 and 14 years old has been children they hurt Big young people between Women to men than 1.5-2 times more gets sick In the article this of the disease causes, symptoms, diagnosis, modern of medicine disease about achieved achievements and modern treatment methods about thought is conducted .

Materials and styles: In the article one series study manual textbooks analysis, scientific books and modern information technologies such as scientific research of means was used.

In rheumatism inflammation heart-blood vein system, nervous system system, joints and to the skin effect shows. First in line, big pressure under working joints will be damaged. In illness in hands, fingers, shoulder and on the knee chronic repeated standing pains, muscles hard being hard stay or subtlety, different different swelling cases, joint and in the muscles of mobility

difficult pass such as symptoms to the body will come. The first symptoms of rheumatism 1-5 weeks from angina after surface comes out.

Modern medicine rheumatism the disease cause release possible 3 that are main factor differentiates These are:

- 1) Streptococcus infection appear to be take coming diseases (Scarlatina, chronic tonsillitis, medium listen inflammation and others);
- 2) Allergy;
- 3) Genetic inclination

Results and discussion: Rheumatism is difficult to treat because it is a disease of mixed immunological-bacteriological nature. Complete treatment is also impossible. In the United States, rheumatic diseases are divided into 10 main categories according to the nomenclature proposed by the American College of Rheumatology in 1838.

These are:

- Consolidator of tissues diffuse diseases;
- Rheumatoid arthritis;
- Adult not enough arthritis;
- Systematic red volchanka;
- Sjogren syndrome;
- Polymyositis;
- Dermatomyositis;
- Behçet disease;
- Psoriasis arthritis.

This diseases common name "Rheumatism". with is called Today's in the day rheumatism to diseases diagnosis to put and treatment works with engaged in "Rheumatology" of medicine called separately department there is and this in the department Rheumatologist doctors activity they run

Rheumatism to diseases diagnosis to put for patients the first in line which symptoms in itself when they feel it to the doctor appeal to do need said to the question, as follows answer we give:

- In the body one how many in the joints pain, swelling, joints hard stay or to soften stay circumstances;
- Most of the time in the morning observable in the body pains;
- Too bad except strong fatigue;
- Fever;

- Heart in the field observable weak pain, heart uneven hit
- A little movement from doing after appear to be strong panting;
- Immunologic violations;
- Mobility too much except weak, strong tiredness

Of the disease risk Factors: These symptoms another one series that it is also found in diseases because of, exactly how circumstances rheumatism for risk factor to be possible to know each one of us for important. Genetics this risk factors inside separately appropriate. Man leukocyte antigen in genes change with born if, then rheumatism development one how many equal to high to the indicator have will be Man's excess obesity, smoking tendency to rheumatism development and deterioration reason will be.

Of the disease clinical to the signs according to Classification: Rheumatism illness of processes to himself special course, clinical features 5 according to in appearance surface comes out

- Sharp in the form of temperature up to 38-40⁰ C rising, joints swelling, exudates appear will be Redness of the skin, inflammation sure surface comes out
- Half sharp in the form of subfertile (body below 38 °C temperature) body temperature will be Even some one in patients inflammation is not observed. They are only arthralgia that is, pain they feel themselves.
- latent form patients himself they feel bad , a lot body sweats the temperature is also low . Organism streptococcus to the antigen suitable immune shifts harvest does
- Elongated appearance basically old old in people observed. Pain, joints one how many months during swelling, mobility significant level decline observed.
- Repeated appearance basically will be and in teenagers observed. Central nerve system damaged, chorea surface will come.

Of the disease which to the member effect to show according to type:

- Heart in the form of of the heart muscles will be damaged. Pain is individual differently surface comes out Sharp heart lack of take will come.
- Joint in the form of first big joints, later small ones will be damaged. Very strong pains the patient is observed movement it becomes difficult.
- Neurological shape rarely cases occurs. To move answer giving the brain cells will be damaged. The patient actions own at will does not obey.
- Skin shape on the skin rashes, rheumatic nodes harvest to be with will pass

- Ophthalmological shape of the eye net to the curtain effect shows. Partially or complete to blindness take will come.
- Lungs shape bronchitis or pleurisy in the form of manifestation will be Rarely observed.

Diagnosis: When diagnosing rheumatic diseases, patients are first subjected to physical examinations by rheumatologists. Blood tests are conducted. Because the disease has many symptoms, the "Kiesel criteria" are used to diagnose the disease. "Kisel criteria" consists of main and additional parts, and the main criteria include:

- Polyarthritis, rheumocarditis, juvantibus confirmation, chorea and others

Additional criteria:

Clinical checks: arthralgia, fast exhaustion, from the nose blood departure, capillary of conductivity increase.

Laboratory checks: neutrophil leukocytosis, erythrocyte drowning speed, C- reactive protein appear to be and another one series tests.

X-ray: To rheumatism diagnosis to put in the process joint on a radiograph observable changes analysis to do important.

UTT examination: Mainly swollen areas are examined. This method is effective because X-rays cannot be used in the early stages of the disease. It is important to determine which joint polyarticular is involved in the disease.

EKG test: records the strength and timing of the heart's activity and shows abnormal rhythms. Important in the diagnosis of heart muscle damage.

Blood tests:

- Test to determine the level of uric acid;
- Test for rheumatoid factor;
- Test for C-reactive protein;
- Antinuclear antibody test.

Treatment of rheumatism: After receiving the results of the analysis, the rheumatologist develops an individual treatment strategy for each person, depending on the characteristics and levels of the disease. But it should not be forgotten that rheumatism is difficult to treat. In order to better treat the disease, it is necessary to speed up the process of diagnosis as much as possible, to establish control over the strict adherence to treatment procedures. In order to prevent the inflammatory process, various antibiotics, drugs designed to stop the activity of streptococcal infection are prescribed by the doctor based on a specific prescription.

Antibiotic treatment: Antibiotic treatment mainly uses drugs designed to stop the life activity of streptococcal bacteria, which are the infectious source of the disease. This method of treatment consists of 2 stages, in the 1st active stage, antibiotics are taken orally. It is carried out within 10 to 14 days. After this stage, the streptococcus bacterium remains in the body, because

this bacterium produces substances that can break down the antibiotic. The 2nd passive phase is continued after 3 weeks of the 1st phase. At this stage, the drug is injected between the muscles. This method of treatment is carried out gradually for 5-6 years, and the result is a reduction of the probability of disease progression and the possibility of heart defects and various vices.

Hormonal treatment: In severe forms of the disease, a certain level of stability can be achieved with the help of hormones prescribed in specific doses.

Biologics: Biologics such as adalimumab, etanercept, and infliximab are new modern forms of treatment. It is used together with disease-modifying rheumatic drugs, when their effect is ineffective. They are injected into the blood. Side effects are mild.

JAK inhibitors: Used in older adults who have failed disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs and biologics. Usually, with Methotrexate, it is taken separately if the patient cannot take Methotrexate.

NSAIDs (non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs): These drugs help relieve pain and reduce inflammation. Medicines must be taken according to a specific doctor's prescription, as they destroy the mucous membrane that protects the stomach from the effects of acid. Medications are often given with a proton pump inhibitor (PPI).

Supportive treatments: Physiotherapy – improves muscle strength and keeps joints flexible. Joint pain can be relieved using transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS).

Occupational therapy includes exercises and advice to prevent pain in everyday activities.

Podiatry - when the disease causes more foot problems, the podiatrist recommends special shoes and various exercises.

Surgery: When joint damage persists despite multiple medications, surgery is performed to restore joint function.

Synovectomy: A type of surgery aimed at reducing pain and improving joint flexibility by removing the inflamed lining of the joint.

Arthroscopy: An arthroscope with a light and camera is inserted into the joint through a small skin incision to remove inflamed tissue. Arthroscopy does not require a long hospital stay, but you should rest under strict supervision for several days.

Arthroplasty: Sometimes patients seek arthroplasty for partial or total replacement of large joints. Prostheses placed in this operation serve the patient for 10-20 years. Some functions are not restored after the joint is replaced with a prosthesis.

Diets: Diet, energy level and allergic properties of food can cause worsening of rheumatism. Eating foods rich in unsaturated fats such as vegetables, fruits, beans, fish, and olive oil are thought to improve rheumatism.

Assistive Devices: Assistive Devices reduces joint pain. For example, a kitchen knife equipped with a handle helps to protect the joints of the fingers and wrists and facilitate movement.

Disease prevention: To prevent the disease, first of all, eliminate the factors that cause the development of streptococcal infection, lead a healthy lifestyle, pay attention to our health, stay away from risk factors that have a negative effect on our nervous system as much as possible. we should try to operate in good conditions and social environment. Maintaining good hygiene is our best defense against disease.

Conclusion: Since rheumatism has a negative effect on the organs that ensure the functionality of our body, such as the joints and the heart, it is appropriate to take this disease seriously, and if we suspect that we or someone close to us has rheumatism, we should consult a doctor. Knowing that modern medical devices are important for early diagnosis of rheumatism, the production of effective drugs, it is important to carry out improvement work on them, to develop treatment

measures that allow full correction of rheumatism. Patients should be referred for early diagnosis and prompt treatment.

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